

Marine Conservation Project Mapping in Macaronesia

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1. Overview

This report presents the results of a mapping exercise of marine and coastal conservation initiatives across Macaronesia, covering the Azores, Madeira, the Canary Islands and Cape Verde. It identifies potential opportunities for Oceans 5 donor organisations to support marine protection in the region, in line with the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and the 30×30 target of conserving at least 30% of coastal and marine areas by 2030 [1,2,6,10,14,19]. In total, 65 projects were identified and analysed, providing an evidence base to inform future funding decisions.

Beyond its ecological relevance, Macaronesia represents a strategic socio-ecological region at the intersection of European, African, and Atlantic governance systems. Its oceanic connectivity, high levels of endemism, and dependence on marine resources make the region particularly relevant for testing integrated approaches to biodiversity conservation, climate adaptation, and sustainable blue economy transitions [4,7,8,14,19,20].

At the same time, the region reflects important asymmetries in institutional capacity, funding access, and governance frameworks, particularly between EU outermost regions and West African island states. These asymmetries reinforce the importance of transnational cooperation and equitable funding mechanisms capable of supporting long-term marine conservation outcomes across the wider Atlantic context [4,8,9,18,19].

2. Methodology

This review was based on an analysis of publicly available information (including research projects, reports, and online databases) on marine conservation projects in the Macaronesia region, following a thorough search to ensure comprehensive coverage and rigor in the selection of relevant initiatives. For the purposes of this study, marine conservation is understood as the integrated protection and management of marine, coastal, and ocean ecosystems. It encompasses not only the preservation and restoration of species, populations, and habitats, but also the mitigation of human pressures that impact marine biodiversity and ecosystem integrity. The research was conducted using publicly accessible online sources, including European research databases (e.g., CORDIS - EU research results), EU LIFE program project websites, regional marine research and conservation portals (e.g., MARSP, MarineSABRES), and non-governmental organization websites (e.g., SPEA, Loro Parque Fundación). These sources provided reports, project descriptions, press releases, and scientific outputs, allowing for a thorough overview of ongoing marine conservation initiatives in the region.

Projects focused on the exclusive economic zones (EEZs) of Macaronesia (Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands, and Cape Verde) and/or adjacent high seas areas were considered. A total of 151 projects were initially identified, of which 80 had a specific focus on marine conservation and were included in the preliminary dataset (Figure 1). The selection was then refined according to the following criteria: (i) clear alignment with marine and coastal conservation objectives, (ii) concrete implementation of activities within the Macaronesia

region, and (iii) availability of formal and verifiable documentation of activities, results, and funding. In addition, priority was given to more recent projects initiated from 2019 onwards, as well as projects started before 2019 that were either recently completed or still ongoing, since this timeframe provided the most representative overview of the current funding landscape.

After applying these criteria, 65 projects were considered for the final analysis (Figure 1). The remaining 71 projects were excluded because they did not meet the inclusion criteria. The analysis of the selected projects included aspects such as objectives, areas proposed for protection, target species and habitats, main environmental pressures, involved partners, budget, and project duration. The complete list of mapped projects can be found in Annex I (see Excel file [here](#)).

Figure 1. Project selection process showing identification, screening, and inclusion steps. A total of 65 projects were finally included in the study.

3. Results

3.1 Geographic Distribution and Project Dimensions

The 65 marine conservation projects analysed are distributed across the Macaronesia region, encompassing the Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands, and Cape Verde. As shown in Figure 2, the distribution of projects is relatively balanced across the three northern archipelagos, with 40 projects in the Canary Islands, 37 in Madeira, 32 in the Azores, and 19 in Cape Verde. It is important to note that several initiatives operate across more than one archipelago, involving shared activities, partnerships, or study areas that connect different parts of the region.

The mapping highlights an active network of marine conservation initiatives across the region, with the northern archipelagos (Azores, Madeira, and Canary Islands) concentrating nearly 69% of all initiatives identified. Around one-fifth (19%) of the projects bridge northern and southern Macaronesian territories, establishing transatlantic cooperation with Cape Verde. Meanwhile, 13% focus exclusively on Cape Verde. This spatial pattern appears to be associated with the institutional capacity and closer integration of these

territories within European research frameworks and funding mechanisms. In contrast, Cape Verde shows a smaller yet significant number of initiatives, suggesting growing engagement in marine protection within the West African coastal zone. The predominance of projects concentrated in the northern archipelagos also reflects broader geopolitical and financial asymmetries in access to European research infrastructures, scientific networks, and institutional capacities. While this concentration has enabled the consolidation of advanced conservation and governance initiatives, it simultaneously highlights the need to strengthen scientific and institutional support for southern Macaronesian territories, particularly Cape Verde. The results further suggest that marine conservation in Macaronesia increasingly operates through interconnected regional governance networks rather than isolated site-based interventions. This tendency is particularly relevant in the context of migratory species conservation, marine spatial planning, and the development of transboundary ecosystem-based management approaches.

Figure 2. Geographic and financial distribution of marine conservation projects across the Macaronesia region. The size of each circle represents the total value of projects in which each archipelago is involved, including shared budgets across multiple territories. The numbers inside the circles indicate the total number of projects, and the colored bars illustrate the relative distribution of ecological, social, institutional, and economic dimensions in each archipelago.

Each colored bar adjacent to the circles in Figure 2 represents the proportional distribution of the dimensions (ecological, economic, social) of projects within each region: ecological (blue), economic (yellow), social (pink), and institutional (purple). The percentages are calculated based on the total number of projects mapped in each archipelago, acknowledging that individual projects may address more than one dimension and, in some cases, operate across multiple regions.

Across the region, ecological and institutional dimensions are the most prevalent, reflecting a predominant focus on biodiversity conservation, marine protected areas (MPAs), and the development of governance frameworks. Social and economic components are also consistently represented, contributing to a diversified portfolio of marine conservation initiatives throughout the region.

To complement the spatial mapping, a financial layer was incorporated into the visualization. In Figure 2, the size of each circle represents the total value of all projects in which each archipelago is involved. Since many initiatives operate across more than one territory, the associated funding is shared among multiple regions, rather than being exclusive to a single location. This approach provides an overview of the level of funding allocated to each archipelago, reflecting both individual and collaborative engagement in marine conservation efforts. The numbers inside the circles indicate the total number of projects, and the colored bars represent the relative distribution of the ecological, social, institutional, and economic dimensions in each archipelago.

The financial distribution indicates that the Azores and Madeira concentrate the largest shares of total investment, reflecting their stronger integration within European research and conservation programmes compared with the other Macaronesian countries. The Canary Islands also show significant funding engagement, supported by a broad portfolio of EU and national initiatives. In contrast, Cape Verde, while representing a smaller financial volume, is particularly focused on biodiversity conservation and regional cooperation between Europe and West Africa.

When considering the region as a whole (Figure 3), the ecological dimension is represented in almost all initiatives (64 projects), followed by the institutional dimension (60 projects). Social (39 projects) and economic (20 projects) occur less frequently but still demonstrate a relevant presence across multiple initiatives. It is important to note that each project may address more than one dimension, as many initiatives integrate ecological, social, institutional, and economic activities within their scope. This pattern reflects the predominance of environmental and governance approaches in marine conservation projects in Macaronesia, while also highlighting the inclusion of social and economic considerations within a subset of initiatives.

Figure 3. Number of projects in which each dimension (ecological, social, institutional, and economic) is represented across the Macaronesia region ($n = 65$ projects mapped).

Overall, the spatial pattern indicates that research needs and funding of conservation projects in Macaronesia are driving an interconnected system of conservation efforts, likely due to the fact that islands share ecological challenges but differ in their institutional capacities and socioeconomic contexts.

3.2. Projects' Implementation Periods

The analysis of 65 marine conservation projects in the Macaronesian region revealed a temporal distribution spanning from 2017 to 2030. Regarding their current status, 29 projects have been completed, 34 remain active, and 2 are still under development (Figure 4). A marked increase in the number of projects initiated after 2019 was observed, reflecting a growing interest and investment in marine conservation initiatives across the region.

In terms of duration, the projects showed an average length of approximately 3.5 years, with considerable variability. These range from short-term projects lasting one to two years, typically focused on pilot activities, localized studies, or specific monitoring programs, to long-term initiatives extending over 8 to 11 years that integrate ecological, social, and institutional components and engage multiple organizations.

Figure 4. Timeline of marine and coastal conservation projects mapped in the Macaronesia region, showing their implementation periods between 2017 and 2030 ($n = 65$ projects mapped).

3.3. Main Direct Drivers

According to IPBES (2019), direct drivers are the factors that directly and indirectly cause the loss of marine biodiversity and the degradation of marine ecosystem services. The five major direct drivers are land and sea use change, overexploitation of species, climate change, pollution, and invasive species.

Our analysis indicates that climate change (44%), pollution (37%), and data scarcity/knowledge gaps (37%) are the most frequently addressed direct drivers across the mapped initiatives in the Macaronesia region (Figure 5). These three factors dominate the projects analysed, reflecting their pervasive influence on marine and coastal ecosystems, from rising sea temperatures and ocean acidification to waste discharge and the lack of

consistent environmental data needed to support management decisions. The prominence of climate change and pollution across the mapped portfolio reflects the growing recognition that marine conservation in island systems cannot be separated from broader global environmental transformations. Rising sea temperatures, ocean acidification, extreme climatic events, and cumulative pollution pressures are increasingly altering ecosystem functioning, species distribution, and the resilience of coastal communities throughout Macaronesia [11,12,14,20]. Likewise, the strong presence of data scarcity and knowledge gaps among the identified drivers highlights that limited access to harmonized and long-term environmental information remains a structural barrier to effective marine governance and evidence-based policy implementation [3,7,8,16,17,20].

Following these, habitat loss (32%), demographic pressure (24%), and overfishing (16%) also emerge as recurrent drivers, highlighting the intensifying human presence in coastal areas and the continuing dependence of island economies on marine resources. These pressures illustrate the challenges of achieving sustainable resource management in regions where ecological and socioeconomic systems are deeply interconnected.

Finally, a set of more localized or emerging pressures, including bycatch (10%), marine traffic (8%), invasive species (7%), and conflicting maritime uses (5%), appear less frequently but indicate growing awareness of their cumulative and long-term impacts. These findings underscore the need for targeted monitoring and policy coordination to mitigate their effects on biodiversity and ecosystem resilience.

Figure 5. Bar chart representing the main direct drivers addressed by the mapped projects in the Macaronesia region (n = 65 projects mapped).

Overall, the diversity of drivers represented in the mapped projects reflects the complex interplay between global, regional, and local stressors affecting Macaronesian

marine systems. This combination of long-recognized and emerging pressures underscores the need for integrated management strategies capable of addressing multiple threats simultaneously while promoting ecosystem resilience and sustainable blue economy pathways.

3.4. Focal Taxa

Seven main focal taxonomic groups were identified to categorize the focus of marine conservation projects in the Macaronesia region. Among them, marine megafauna was used to group projects that addressed large marine species simultaneously, such as marine mammals, sea turtles, seabirds, and sharks. Other projects, however, focused exclusively on specific groups, including seabirds, cetaceans, benthic communities, elasmobranchs, deep-sea and pelagic ecosystems, or seals. This classification approach reflects both broadly focused projects and those targeting specific taxonomic groups. The results highlight the ecological and thematic diversity of the initiatives, with a predominance of efforts directed toward charismatic species of high ecological and socioeconomic importance (Figure 6).

Projects addressing marine megafauna were the most frequently represented, totaling 15 initiatives (37.5%). This category includes groups such as marine mammals, seabirds, sea turtles, and large pelagic fish (e.g., sharks and rays), reflecting the regional interest in species widely recognized for their ecological roles and their potential to raise public awareness. Examples include the loggerhead turtle (*Caretta caretta*), the Azores bullfinch (*Pyrrhula murina*), and several Macaronesian seabird species such as *Bulweria bulwerii* and *Calonectris borealis*.

While megafauna projects tend to adopt broader and more integrative approaches, other initiatives focus on more specific taxonomic levels, aiming to deepen knowledge about the ecology, threats, and management strategies of particular groups. Among these, projects dedicated exclusively to seabirds (8 projects) stand out, addressing species such as the Brown Booby (*Sula leucogaster*), Red-billed Tropicbird (*Phaethon aethereus*), Cape Verde Shearwater (*Calonectris edwardsii*), Manx Shearwater (*Puffinus puffinus*), and Balearic Shearwater (*P. mauretanicus*). Cetacean-focused projects (6 projects) included species such as the bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*) and the short-finned pilot whale (*Globicephala macrorhynchus*). For benthic communities (4 projects), efforts included the study and conservation of organisms such as rhodolith-forming algae (maerl) and black corals (*Antipathella wollastoni*).

Elasmobranchs (4 projects) also feature prominently, indicating growing attention to the conservation of sharks and rays, particularly vulnerable species such as the angelshark (*Squatina squatina*), which has been historically affected by overfishing and habitat degradation. A smaller number of initiatives targeted pelagic and deep-sea ecosystems (2 projects) and seals (1 project), including one focused on the Mediterranean monk seal (*Monachus monachus*), reflecting an emerging interest in less-studied but ecologically significant components of marine biodiversity.

Finally, 25 projects presented other thematic focuses, without targeting a specific biological group. These projects address integrated aspects of conservation and ecosystem

management, including environmental monitoring, marine spatial planning, and the sustainable use of marine resources.

Figure 6. Focal Taxa: Proportion (%) of marine conservation projects in the Macaronesian region according to their focal taxa, including marine megafauna, seabirds, benthic communities, cetaceans, elasmobranchs, deep-sea and pelagic ecosystems, and seals ($n = 40$ projects mapped).

3.5 Research Themes

The table below presents the main research themes addressed in the analysed projects in the Macaronesia region, along with the number of occurrences (n) and the specific contents related to each theme (Table 1). The results reveal a broad range of approaches encompassing ecological, socioeconomic, and technological dimensions. Among the most prominent themes, *Biodiversity* ($n = 29$) stands out as a central focus of regional initiatives, confirming the key role of biological diversity in guiding conservation efforts. The most recurrent approaches include the conservation and monitoring of marine biodiversity, the assessment and protection of threatened species, and the identification of Key Biodiversity Areas (KBAs). These results highlight the ecological foundation of conservation actions in the region, which serve as a basis for environmental management, monitoring, and policy development.

Next, the themes related to *Community Involvement & Stakeholder Engagement* ($n = 17$) and *Conservation* ($n = 16$) stand out. These results indicate a growing recognition of the importance of social participation and collaborative governance in marine management, including practices such as citizen science, capacity building, and the development of participatory governance. The initiatives categorized under *Conservation* mainly addressed area planning and prioritization, evidence-based strategies, and long-term monitoring.

Other themes with notable representation include *Environmental Impacts and Monitoring* ($n = 16$), *Climate Adaptation and Resilience* ($n = 11$), and *Data and Information*

Management (n = 10), reflecting the strengthening of environmental monitoring practices and analytical tools for impact assessment and climate adaptation. In addition, emerging themes such as *Blue Economy and Sustainable Development*, *Artificial Intelligence and Technology*, and *Circular Economy and Waste Management* point to the incorporation of innovative and sustainable approaches in marine management processes.

The thematic diversity identified across the projects reflects an ongoing transition from traditional biodiversity conservation approaches toward more integrated socio-ecological frameworks. This evolution is particularly visible in the increasing incorporation of governance innovation, ecosystem services, climate resilience, participatory management, and digital monitoring technologies into marine conservation initiatives. Nevertheless, the relatively lower representation of socioeconomic, governance, and co-management themes suggests that marine conservation in Macaronesia continues to be predominantly science-driven and ecologically oriented, with more limited incorporation of distributive justice, social equity, and livelihood-related dimensions.

Particular attention should be given to the themes *Marine Protected Areas* (MPA) (n = 11) and *Marine Spatial Planning* (MSP) (n = 6), both directly relevant to the scope of the ongoing study. MPAs are among the most established topics, reflecting their central role in biodiversity conservation and the maintenance of ecosystem services. Projects addressing this theme typically involve adaptive management, species and habitat monitoring, and integration with public policies and coastal planning instruments.

In addition to cross-cutting themes, several projects focus on specific focal groups, reflecting ecological and strategic priorities in marine conservation. Among them, *Cetaceans and Marine Mammals* (n = 7) stand out, with an emphasis on marine mammal conservation, cetacean monitoring, and mitigation of ship strikes; *Seabirds* (n = 9), involving conservation, monitoring, and ecological studies of these birds; and *Benthic* (n = 8), targeting deep-sea ecosystems, benthic habitat mapping, and the removal of coastal and seabed debris. Attention is also given to *Bycatch and Fisheries Interactions* (n = 8), highlighting efforts to understand and mitigate the negative impacts of fisheries on these focal groups. These themes indicate efforts directed toward strategic species and ecosystems, often serving as indicators of environmental health and the integrity of marine ecosystems.

Overall, the results indicate a significant concentration of efforts in biodiversity conservation, environmental monitoring, and ecosystem management, while also reflecting thematic diversification and the emergence of new areas focused on sustainability, technological innovation, and participatory governance in the Macaronesia region.

Table 1. Distribution of projects by main research themes and number of related contents ($n = 65$ projects mapped).

Research themes	N	Content
Biodiversity	29	Marine biodiversity conservation (21), Biodiversity monitoring and Assessment (7), Key Biodiversity Areas (KBAs) (1)
Community Involvement & Stakeholder Engagement	17	Stakeholder engagement (9), Capacity building (3), Citizen science (3), Participatory governance (2)
Conservation	16	Species conservation (10), Conservation strategies (6)
Environmental Impacts & Monitoring	16	Environmental impacts (6), Pollution (6), Vulnerability (4)
Climate Adaptation & Resilience	11	Climate change (7), Climate and coastal resilience (4)
Marine Protected Areas	11	Marine protected areas (11)
Data & Information Management	10	Marine data management (5), Geospatial analysis (2), Data-gap analysis (3)
Ecosystem Assessment	10	Ecosystem-based management (5), Ecosystem assessment (5)
Habitat Ecology	9	Habitat Restoration (4), Habitat monitoring (3), Habitat conservation (2)
Blue Economy & Sustainable Development	9	Blue economy (6), Sustainable blue tourism (2), Carbon sequestration (1)
Seabirds	9	Seabird conservation (5), Monitoring and ecology of seabirds (4)
Benthic	8	Deep-sea ecosystems (4), Benthic habitat mapping (3), Coastal and seabed debris removal (1)
Acoustics & Monitoring	8	Acoustic monitoring (5), Monitoring technology (3)
Bycatch & Fisheries Interactions	8	Bycatch mitigation (4), Fisheries interactions (4)

Ecosystem Services	8	Ecosystem services (8)
Cetaceans & Marine Mammals	7	Marine mammal conservation (3), Cetacean monitoring (3), Whale-ship collision mitigation (1)
Island Ecosystems & Regional Cooperation	7	Island and Regional ecosystem management (5), Transboundary management (2)
Marine Litter & Microplastics	7	Marine litter (5), Microplastics (2)
Marine Spatial Planning	6	Marine spatial planning (6)
Governance & Policy	6	Marine Policy (4), Marine governance (2)
Circular Economy & Waste Management	6	Waste management (3), Circular economy (2), Lost or Discarded Fishing Gear (1)
Coastal & Marine Habitat Restoration	5	Ecosystem restoration (4), Coastal and marine habitat restoration (1)
Artificial Intelligence & Technology	5	Technological innovation (3), Artificial intelligence (1), Digital twin ocean (1)
Ecotourism	5	Ecotourism (5)
Invasive Species & Predator Control	5	Invasive predator control (5)
Decision Support & Methodology	4	Decision-support tools (4)
Geospatial & Spatial Planning	3	Coastal and Urban Planning (2), Maritime traffic risk mapping (1)
Monitoring Systems & Technology	3	Observation infrastructure (2), Monitoring and modelling of debris (1)
Ocean Literacy & Education	3	Ocean literacy (2), Ocean observation (1)
Genetic Studies	2	Genetics and Laboratory analysis (2)

3.6. Funding Sources

The analysis of funding sources reveals a strong predominance of European Union programmes, which account for 67.5% of the total investment, corresponding to €111 million out of a total of €164.5 million during the period between 2009 and 2030 (Figure 7; Figure 8). This category includes large-scale frameworks such as Horizon Europe, Horizon 2020, LIFE Programme, and the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF). On average, each project mobilizes around €2.5 million, although values vary widely depending on scope, duration, and geographic coverage, from small community-based initiatives to multi-country research consortia. Regional cooperation instruments, such as the INTERREG MAC and INTERREG Atlantic Area programmes, represent around 18.3% of total funding (\approx €30 million). These programmes are particularly relevant for fostering transnational collaboration and strengthening institutional and scientific ties among the archipelagos of Portugal, Spain, and Cape Verde. Funding from private and international sources, represents approximately 11.7% of total resources (\approx €19 million). These initiatives generally support field-based conservation efforts, capacity building, and community-driven marine management. Finally, national and regional funding mechanisms account for about 2.5% of total investment (\approx €4 million), led by entities such as the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT - Portugal), the Government of the Canary Islands, and the Ministry of Agriculture and Environment of Cape Verde.

Overall, this funding landscape highlights a high dependency on EU mechanisms, which serve as the structural backbone for marine conservation in the Macaronesia region. At the same time, regional cooperation and philanthropic contributions play a complementary role, ensuring a diversified mix of governance, scientific, and community-oriented initiatives.

The strong dependence on European funding instruments demonstrates both the opportunities and vulnerabilities of the current conservation landscape. While EU programmes have enabled the development of sophisticated research and governance initiatives, they also generate a high degree of financial dependency on external funding cycles and policy priorities [4,9,18,19]. This dependency raises important questions regarding the long-term sustainability of conservation actions once funding periods end, particularly for projects requiring continuous monitoring, governance coordination, and community engagement [10,13,18,19].

Figure 7. Total investment (in million euros) allocated to marine conservation projects by funding category.

Figure 8. Percentage distribution of funded projects by source.

3.7. Marine Spatial Planning & Marine Protected Area

Among the 65 projects analysed, Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) are referenced more frequently than Marine Spatial Planning (MSP), 61% of the initiatives include direct actions related to the establishment, management, or monitoring of MPAs, reflecting the central role of protected areas in marine conservation strategies across Macaronesia (Table 2). In contrast, Marine Spatial Planning is present in about 34% of the mapped projects, generally associated with integrated management efforts and cross-sectoral coordination (Table 2).

The growing overlap between Marine Spatial Planning and Marine Protected Area approaches suggests an emerging transition toward more integrated ocean governance frameworks in the region. Such integration is increasingly recognized as essential for balancing biodiversity conservation with competing maritime activities, including fisheries, tourism, maritime transport, renewable energy, and coastal development [5,9,10,13,15,18]. The integration of both components occurs in roughly one-third of the initiatives (31%), demonstrating a moderate but growing alignment between spatial planning instruments and conservation measures. Projects exclusively dedicated to MSP (3%) often emphasize cross-sectoral coordination, maritime uses, and data integration, while those centered solely on MPAs (31%) prioritize biodiversity conservation (Table 3). Finally, around 36% of the projects do not explicitly address either MSP or MPA objectives but still contribute indirectly through themes such as marine litter management, blue economy development, or climate resilience (Table 3).

Table 2. Presence of Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) or Marine Protected Areas (MPA) components across the mapped projects in the Macaronesia region.

Category	Yes	No	% of projects
Marine Spatial Planning (MSP)	22	43	≈ 34%
Marine Protected Area (MPA)	40	25	≈ 61%

The spatial distribution of projects across coastal and oceanic environments reveals a clear imbalance toward nearshore ecosystems. Out of the 65 initiatives analysed, one-third (33%) are focused exclusively on coastal areas, while oceanic or pelagic environments represent only 14% of the portfolio. The majority (53%) operate across both realms, often integrating coastal management and offshore conservation measures.

When cross-referenced with the MSP–MPA classification, most coastal projects fall within MPA-only or indirect categories, reflecting site-based conservation, restoration, or pollution management approaches. In contrast, oceanic projects, though fewer in number, tend to combine MSP and MPA elements, particularly in transnational or research-driven programmes such as Mission Atlantic and Marine SABRES. This pattern underscores the need to expand integrated planning and protection efforts beyond coastal waters to advance toward the 30×30 global targets. This imbalance also suggests that offshore and pelagic ecosystems continue to receive comparatively less institutional and financial attention despite

their strategic role in biodiversity connectivity, climate regulation, migratory corridors, and ecosystem resilience across the wider Atlantic region.

Table 3. Integration of Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) and Marine Protected Areas (MPA) within projects by focus (Coastal, Oceanic, Both).

Category	Coastal	Oceanic	Both (Coastal & Oceanic)	Projects	% of total Projects
Both MSP and MPA	1	3	16	20	31%
MSP only	1	0	1	2	3%
MPA only	8	1	11	20	31%
Indirectly MSP nor MPA	11	6	6	23	36%
Total	21 (32%)	9 (15%)	34 (53%)	65 (100%)	

3.8 Fisheries Component

Among the 65 projects analysed, 7 initiatives ($\approx 10\%$) address fisheries directly, focusing on topics such as sustainable resource use, bycatch reduction, and community-based management (e.g., REDUCE, Marine Beacon, PaMAR, COAST). Another 29 projects ($\approx 45\%$) include fisheries indirectly, often through activities related to marine spatial planning, blue economy development, species conservation, or marine litter reduction that influence fisheries management frameworks (Figure 9). The remaining 29 projects ($\approx 45\%$) have no direct link to fisheries.

Figure 9. Distribution of projects according to the presence of a fisheries component (direct, indirect, or none).

Geographically, fisheries-related projects are more frequent in Cape Verde and transatlantic initiatives connecting the southern and northern archipelagos, where fishing plays a stronger socioeconomic role. Overall, the analysis highlights that while fisheries are not the primary focus of most initiatives, they represent an essential cross-cutting theme that connects conservation, livelihoods, and sustainable ocean governance across the Macaronesia region.

3.9 Socio-ecological Connectivity

Regarding the potential for socio-ecological connectivity between the Macaronesia region and the European and/or African continents (e.g., migratory species or European/African partners), 53 of the projects ($\approx 81.5\%$) showed evidence of connectivity, 10 ($\approx 15.4\%$) did not provide sufficient information, and 2 ($\approx 3\%$) could not be assessed (N/A).

To deepen the understanding of the nature of the observed socio-ecological connectivity, the projects were classified into two main dimensions: ecological connectivity and governance-oriented connectivity. It was observed that most initiatives ($\approx 71\%$) were predominantly associated with the ecological dimension, while approximately 29% focused on governance-related aspects (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Distribution of projects according to the main type of socio-ecological connectivity.

Projects considered under the ecological connectivity category focused mainly on migratory species, such as seabirds, cetaceans, and migratory fishes, that depend on interconnected marine habitats and corridors linking the Macaronesian archipelagos to adjacent regions. These initiatives emphasized ecological linkages such as breeding and feeding routes, species movements between islands, and the integration of scientific data into management instruments, with the aim of strengthening ecosystem-based approaches.

On the other hand, projects classified under the governance category addressed institutional and management connections across different jurisdictions. These included, for example, shared governance platforms for the Atlantic and Indian Ocean basins, ecosystem-based marine spatial planning (MSP) methods, data-sharing mechanisms, and coordinated conservation actions among the archipelagos. Other examples involved participatory and conservation networks aimed at addressing environmental impacts that transcend national boundaries.

These results suggest that, while ecological factors constitute the primary pathway for socio-ecological connectivity in the region, governance-oriented collaborations also play a key role in supporting integrated and ecosystem-based management across Macaronesia and its wider transregional context.

3.10 Institutional connectivity

In terms of the partners involved, most projects included government, public administration or public research bodies (52 projects; 80%), followed by academic institutions (47; 72%), NGO or non-profit organisations (37; 57%) and private companies (21; 32%). Eighteen percent of projects (12; 18%) included partners from all four sectors. Tables 4 to 7 indicate the institutions which feature most frequently in the funded projects according to sector, as well as their region, country or island. Overall, partners are most frequently situated in Spain and Portugal (including Canary Islands, Azores, Madeira), France, Germany, Denmark, the United Kingdom, Ireland, Norway, the Netherlands and Italy.

Table 4. Partner sectors involved in funded projects, including MPAs Canary Islands as Project 65.

Type of partner/institution	Number of projects	% of projects; n = 65
Government, public administration or public research bodies	52	80%
Academic institutions	47	72%
NGOs or non-profit organisations	38	58%
Private companies	21	32%
Projects involving partners from all four sectors	12	18%

4. Analytical Summary of Results

The mapping of 65 marine conservation projects across the Macaronesia region reveals a dynamic and interconnected landscape of initiatives addressing multiple ecological, social, and governance dimensions. Collectively, these projects demonstrate the consolidation

of a regional network of conservation actions that combine local priorities with broader international agendas for marine sustainability.

From a spatial perspective, the northern archipelagos, Azores, Madeira, and Canary Islands, maintain a relatively balanced concentration of projects, reflecting their established institutional capacity and strong integration within European research and funding frameworks, which together account for nearly 67.5% of the total investment (€164.5 million). Cape Verde, although less represented in numerical terms, contributes significantly to transboundary initiatives, fostering South-North cooperation and extending the region's ecological and governance connectivity toward the West African coastal systems.

Across all archipelagos, ecological and institutional dimensions remain predominant, emphasizing biodiversity conservation, marine protected areas (MPAs), and the strengthening of governance frameworks. Social and economic components are also consistently integrated into a subset of initiatives that connect conservation objectives to community-based management and sustainable blue economy pathways.

The analysis of direct drivers highlights *climate change*, *pollution*, and *data scarcity or knowledge gaps*, followed by *habitat loss* and *overfishing*, as the most recurrent pressures, reinforcing the need for cross-sectoral strategies and funding capable of addressing cumulative and transboundary impacts on marine ecosystems.

In terms of policy instruments, Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) emerge as the most recurrent management tool (61% of projects), confirming their central role in regional conservation policies. Marine Spatial Planning (MSP), present in 34% of the mapped initiatives, represents an expanding approach to integrate multiple maritime uses and reduce spatial conflicts. Strengthening the articulation between MPA and MSP initiatives, which currently overlap in roughly one-third of the projects, could enhance ecosystem connectivity and support a more coherent and adaptive regional ocean governance framework.

Taken together, the results suggest that Macaronesia is evolving toward a multi-level governance system in which local conservation actions are increasingly connected to regional, European, and global environmental agendas. This creates opportunities for policy coherence and transnational conservation planning, but also requires stronger coordination mechanisms capable of integrating ecological, institutional, and socioeconomic priorities across scales. Importantly, the region's strategic position between Europe and Africa offers significant potential for developing innovative models of transboundary marine governance capable of addressing shared challenges related to biodiversity loss, fisheries sustainability, climate adaptation, and ocean equity.

Despite the significant progress achieved, the analysis also identifies gaps and opportunities. Themes such as data harmonization, standardization of monitoring efforts, and the integration of social and economic dimensions remain unevenly addressed. Moreover, limited attention to oceanic waters, deep-sea ecosystems and invasive species suggests areas where future initiatives could advance regional knowledge and management capacity.

Overall, the results underscore the importance of regional cooperation, knowledge sharing, and institutional alignment to strengthen the effectiveness of marine conservation across Macaronesia. Ensuring and prioritizing the participation of Cape Verde in transnational initiatives will be essential to achieve a more balanced regional representation and to fully

leverage the ecological and socioeconomic diversity of Macaronesia. By fostering inclusive collaboration, leveraging existing synergies, and addressing the identified gaps, the region can serve as a model of transnational cooperation for biodiversity conservation and sustainable ocean governance.

5. Mapping of Active and Upcoming Projects

This section provides a consolidated overview of the active and upcoming marine conservation projects identified across the Macaronesia region. The mapping captures 34 initiatives currently under implementation or in the process of securing funding, representing the most up-to-date snapshot of the regional conservation landscape. These projects collectively reflect the diversity of approaches, funding mechanisms, and governance models supporting marine biodiversity protection, ecosystem restoration, and sustainable ocean management in the Macaronesia region. Each project was classified according to four analytical criteria:

1. Marine Spatial Planning (MSP): indicating projects that contribute to spatial management and ecosystem-based planning;
2. Marine Protected Area (MPA): covering initiatives that establish, manage, or monitor marine protected zones;
3. EU Funding: highlighting projects financed by major European instruments such as *Horizon Europe*, *LIFE*, or *Interreg MAC 2021–2027*;
4. Multi-region Scope: referring to initiatives implemented across more than one Macaronesian archipelago, enhancing regional connectivity and knowledge transfer.

Table 5. Active and Upcoming Marine Conservation Projects in the Macaronesia Region (2024–2030).

Title of the Project	MSP	MPA	EU Funding	Multi-region
Marine SABRES	✓	✓	✓	✓
LIFE Natura@night	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mission Atlantic	✓	✓	✓	✓
REDUCE	✓	✓	✓	✓
LIFE IP Azores Natura	✓	✓	✓	✓
BLUE CONNECT	✓	✓	✓	✓
LIFE Garachico	✓		✓	✓
MarinePlan	✓	✓	✓	
Macaronesia Marine Sanctuary (MMS)	✓	✓		✓
LIFE4BEST- Regional Ecosystem Profile		✓	✓	✓
ECOMARIS	✓		✓	✓
AMPLIAMAR	✓	✓	✓	

LIFE INTEMARES	✓	✓	✓	
SEAMPHONI	✓	✓	✓	
Conservation Strategies for Sharks	✓	✓	✓	
MARVEL - Madeira	✓	✓	✓	
MAC Puffinus LIFE2030			✓	✓
SEAGHOSTS			✓	✓
IMPLACOST			✓	✓
Blue Azores	✓	✓		
BAIT		✓		
HOPE Macaronesia				✓
Darwin Initiative – Cape Verde				
PaMAR - Cabo Verde		✓		
Marine Beacon			✓	
COAST - Cabo Verde			✓	
ATLANTIC WHALE DEAL				✓
CLIMAREST			✓	
Free LitterAT			✓	
TWILIGHTED			✓	
Angelshark Project		✓		
Conservação de Rayas e Tubarões			✓	
STOP Predators			✓	
MPA Canary Islands	✓	✓		

Table 8 presents the full inventory of active and upcoming initiatives. Table 9 does not reproduce the full inventory; rather, it highlights a selected subset of projects that are particularly relevant for donor engagement, based on their strategic fit, regional significance, and readiness to support practical conservation action.

Across the mapped portfolio, three broad levels of action-readiness can be observed. Policy-enabling initiatives such as Marine SABRES, LIFE Natura@night, REDUCE, MarinePlan, ECOMARIS, and the Macaronesia Marine Sanctuary proposal are especially relevant for strengthening MSP-MPA articulation, transnational cooperation, ecological connectivity, and shared governance across the archipelagos. These initiatives are also important entry points for advancing transnational MPA networks and for extending regional conservation attention toward adjacent high seas and wider oceanic areas, in line with the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and the 30×30 agenda.

Knowledge-generating initiatives such as Mission Atlantic, LIFE INTEMARES, SEAMPHONI, and AMPLIAMAR provide the scientific and monitoring foundations

necessary for evidence-based decision-making and regional data harmonisation. However, where projects remain primarily at the stage of baseline assessment or data generation, without a clear route toward MPA designation, management measures, restoration, enforcement, or policy uptake, they may create a bottleneck between knowledge generation and practical conservation action.

Implementation-oriented initiatives such as LIFE IP Azores Natura, BLUE CONNECT, LIFE Garachico, MPAs Canary Islands, PaMAR, HOPE Macaronesia, Angelshark Project, and Blue Azores demonstrate stronger potential for near-term conservation impact by linking site-based management, restoration, governance, MPA strengthening and creation, and community participation with concrete outcomes. Together, these initiatives reflect a multi-layered governance ecosystem that combines European-led frameworks with locally driven innovation and can help strengthen coordination across the region, including closer cooperation with West African partners.

In the “Main Focus” column of Table 9, K denotes knowledge-generating, P policy-enabling, and I implementation-oriented initiatives. These categories are intended to indicate the predominant stage at which each project contributes to conservation outcomes, rather than to rank projects by overall value. From a donor perspective, implementation-oriented initiatives may offer clearer pathways to near-term conservation impact, while policy-enabling and knowledge-generating initiatives can also be strategic where they help unlock governance change or address clearly identified evidence gaps linked to follow-on action.

Table 6. Selected active and upcoming projects of particular donor relevance.

Project Title	Main Focus	Macaronesian Regions	Funding Type	Potential Engagement
Marine SABRES	(P) MSP/MPA integration; corridors	Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands	Horizon Europe	Co-funding / technical support to strengthen MSP-MPA corridor
LIFE Natura@night	(P) Biodiversity & light pollution	Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands	LIFE Programme	Support for ecosystem-based MSP / biodiversity corridor linkage
Mission Atlantic	(K) Atlantic ecosystem assessments	Azores, Canary Islands	Horizon 2020	Strengthen Atlantic socio-ecological connectivity

REDUCE	(P) Bycatch reduction & Atlantic cooperation	All regions	Horizon Europe	Policy integration & regional data frameworks
LIFE IP Azores Natura	(I) Integrated MPA management	Azores	LIFE Programme	Technical collaboration on participatory MPA governance
BLUE CONNECT	(I) Restoration & conservation planning	All regions	Horizon Europe	Transnational governance & 30×30 alignment
LIFE Garachico	(I) Coastal climate resilience	Azores, Canaries	LIFE Programme	Catalytic funding for replication/continuity
MarinePlan	(P) Science-based MSP	Azores	Horizon Europe	Technical linkage to MSP/MPA frameworks
LIFE INTEMARES	(K) MPA monitoring & Natura 2000	Canary Islands	LIFE Programme	Joint monitoring integration
SEAMPHONI	(K) Digital twin & biodiversity monitoring	Madeira	Horizon Europe	Data interoperability & policy alignment
AMPLIAMAR	(K) Seabird tracking & MPA expansion	Canary Islands	Pleamar Programme	Evidence base for adaptive management
PaMAR (Cabo Verde)	(I) Community-based MPA governance	Cape Verde	Blue Action Fund / Oceans 5	Strengthen local anchoring & replication

HOPE Macaronesia	(I) Education & regional cooperation	Azores, Madeira, Canaries, CV	Interreg MAC	Support microgrants / Blue Partnership facility
Angelshark Project	(I) Species recovery & citizen science	Canary Islands	Private / NGO consortium	Empower local participation & awareness
Blue Azores	(I) Large-scale MPA network	Azores	Private foundation	Coordination with EU frameworks
ECOMARIS	(P) Blue Economy & Spatial Data	Azores, Canaries, Cape Verde	Interreg MAC	Knowledge transfer and MSP data platform
Macaronesia Marine Sanctuary (MMS)	(P) Transnational sanctuary proposal	All regions	Institutional / Private	Policy bridge EU–Africa / Atlantic diplomacy
MPAs Canary Islands	(I) MPA strengthening & creation	Canary Islands	Oceans 5	Catalytic support for MPA strengthening, new designations and regional replication

6. Research Gaps and Recommended Areas for Funding

Our analysis reveals important key geographical, thematic and taxonomic gaps in the implementation of marine conservation efforts across the Macaronesia region. Although a substantial number of EU-funded initiatives (e.g., LIFE, Horizon Europe, INTERREG) have supported biodiversity protection and ecosystem restoration, these efforts have not been evenly distributed. Certain island groups and coastal zones have received sustained investment and scientific attention, while others remain comparatively underrepresented. Similarly, taxonomic focus has tended to concentrate on emblematic or commercially relevant species, leaving many ecologically significant but less visible groups insufficiently studied or managed.

6.1. Geographical Gap

- Cape Verde remains considerably underrepresented in the current portfolio of marine and coastal projects. The country's limited participation in EU-funded mechanisms results in a lower density of ongoing initiatives, leaving important ecosystems and communities with reduced research and conservation coverage.

Recommendation: Promote and financially support Cape Verde's inclusion in transnational and regional programs, either through specific funding calls or through joint EU-African mechanisms to ensure its integration into broader Macaronesian research and conservation frameworks.

6.2. Thematic Gaps

- Adjacent high seas and wider oceanic areas, including Macaronesian deep-sea waters, seamounts and canyons, remain comparatively underrepresented in the current portfolio, despite hosting vulnerable marine ecosystems, biodiversity hotspots, carbon sinks, and ecological corridors of regional significance. Benthic ecosystems are largely unexplored and unprotected across the region. Despite their socio-ecological relevance, these environments have received limited attention in comparison with coastal and pelagic systems.

Recommendation: Develop and fund pilot programmes for adjacent high seas and oceanic governance, deep-sea and benthic monitoring, and blue carbon valuation, integrating sensor networks, in situ sampling (e.g. genetic data, carbon cycling), and conservation-oriented objectives.

- Socioeconomic and governance dimensions are less represented relative to ecological studies. Many projects focus on biodiversity assessment, while fewer address the social and economic dynamics that drive sustainable management. Similarly, there are limited co-management structures and fisher participation strategies while gender and equity dimensions are underrepresented.

Recommendation: Increase funding for interdisciplinary research linking biodiversity conservation to sustainable livelihoods, blue economy models, and governance innovation. Support co-management and participatory marine spatial planning pilots and socio-economic impact modelling for conservation.

- A science-to-action bottleneck remains evident across the regional portfolio. Many initiatives generate robust scientific evidence, monitoring data, or ecological assessments, but fewer are clearly linked to downstream conservation actions such as MPA designation, management plans, restoration, fisheries measures, enforcement, or community co-management.

Recommendation: Prioritize initiatives that connect science and monitoring to operational conservation outcomes, and favour proposals that show a clear implementation pathway or policy uptake strategy.

6.3. Taxonomic Gaps

- Research distribution across taxonomic groups and regions is uneven. Certain groups, such as cetaceans and seabirds, have been studied far more extensively than others. Moreover, while cetaceans have been relatively well studied in the northern archipelagos, they remain markedly understudied in Cape Verde.

Recommendation: Prioritize targeted studies on underrepresented taxa, particularly benthic invertebrates and deep-sea corals, elasmobranchs, and non-commercial fish species, and cetaceans in Cape Verde to strengthen the regional ecological baseline and inform conservation planning.

6.4. Data Integration and Socio-ecological Connectivity Gaps

- The regional fragmentation of data platforms and monitoring systems hinders joint analysis and long-term assessments, especially considering socio-ecological connectivity between the Macaronesia region and the European and/or African continents (e.g. migratory species, European/African partners).

Recommendation: Support the development of interoperable and harmonized sensor and data-sharing networks across archipelagos, enabling standardized observation of key social and marine indicators (e.g. open access data frameworks aligned with the EU Digital Twin standards).

6.5. Transnational Collaboration Gaps

- A particularly promising funding opportunity lies in projects that move beyond isolated site-based protection toward transnational MPA networks and corridor-based protection across Macaronesia. Existing multi-region initiatives already provide a foundation for this through combined MSP–MPA approaches, but further support is needed to translate ecological connectivity and regional cooperation into durable transnational protection, shared governance arrangements, and coordinated monitoring across archipelagos and adjoining Atlantic waters.
- Ecological connectivity and fisheries between African and European waters are closely interlinked. Strengthening collaboration between African and European partners is essential to safeguard ecological corridors, promote sustainable fisheries, and reduce asymmetries in research capacity and access to funding.

Recommendation: Facilitate co-funded programmes that safeguard ecosystem connectivity between the EU and Africa, strengthen links among research institutions, and support the development of transnational MPA networks, corridor-based protection, and coordinated monitoring across archipelagos and adjoining Atlantic waters.

6.6 Institutional Equity Gaps

- While the Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands benefit from EU funding and strong institutional frameworks, Cape Verde remains underrepresented in EU-funded research and capacity-building initiatives, and has unequal access to marine spatial planning expertise, combined with weak infrastructure and data systems.

Recommendation: Create dedicated funds for Cape Verdean partners, support institutional partnerships and exchange programs and promote the co-development of joint EU-Africa marine governance frameworks.

6.7 Policy Coherence Gaps

- Macaronesia acts as a geopolitical and ecological bridge between Europe and Africa, yet project-based cooperation rarely persists beyond short funding cycles. Symptoms include short-term and fragmented collaboration, policy incoherence between EU and African partners and inconsistent MPA and MSP frameworks.

Recommendation: Support the creation of permanent regional cooperation hubs that promote joint policy innovation for ecosystem connectivity and governance alignment. Finance regional dialogues for harmonizing strategies under the 2030 Agenda.

6.8 Long-term Financial Sustainability Gaps

- Many conservation initiatives remain highly dependent on short-term project cycles, creating discontinuities in monitoring, governance implementation, and stakeholder engagement once funding periods conclude. This limits the long-term effectiveness and institutional consolidation of marine conservation efforts across the region.

Recommendation: Promote blended and long-term financing mechanisms that combine EU funding, philanthropic investment, regional public funding, and blue finance instruments to ensure continuity of conservation outcomes beyond individual project cycles.

Table 7. Summary of Gaps and Recommendations.

Gap Identified	Recommended Focus for Funding
Cape Verde underrepresented	Dedicated funding calls; stronger integration in EU–Africa and Macaronesian initiatives
High Seas and adjacent oceanic governance gap	Support planning, monitoring, and protection-oriented governance in adjacent high seas, pelagic corridors, and offshore biodiversity hotspots
Deep-sea and benthic systems	Pilot monitoring and assessment programmes, including blue carbon valuation
Socioeconomic/governance initiatives	Support interdisciplinary, policy-linked research, co-management pilots, participatory MSP, and socio-economic impact modelling
Science-to-action bottleneck	Prioritise projects with clear pathways from research to MPA designation, management, restoration, fisheries measures, enforcement, or community co-management
Limited coverage of non-charismatic species	Targeted research on benthic and deep-sea taxa, elasmobranchs, non-commercial fish species, and cetaceans in Cape Verde
Fragmented monitoring and data systems	Regional sensor, data-sharing, and interoperability networks across archipelagos
Transnational MPA networks	Co-fund corridor-based protection, shared governance, and coordinated monitoring across archipelagos and adjoining Atlantic waters
Weak Africa–EU linkages	Co-funded transnational programmes that strengthen ecological connectivity, fisheries governance, and regional ownership
Institutional and capacity inequity	Institutional partnerships, exchange programmes, and dedicated support for Cape Verdean partners
Weak regional policy coherence	Joint policy innovation hubs and regional dialogue platforms for governance alignment

Funding impact could be amplified by aligning investments with:

- EU Mission Ocean and Horizon Europe priorities
- UN Ocean Decade programs (e.g. Coast Predict, Digital Twin Ocean)
- Regional Action Plans under OSPAR and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)
- Blue Economy frameworks focused on sustainable island development (e.g. UNEP, UNDP).

7. Conclusion

This report consolidates knowledge on marine conservation initiatives across the Macaronesia region, revealing a dynamic network of 65 projects addressing ecological, institutional, social, and economic dimensions while reflecting shared regional challenges and governance asymmetries.

Macaronesia has developed a strong foundation of cooperation, policy innovation, and scientific collaboration, largely supported by European funding mechanisms such as LIFE, Horizon Europe, and INTERREG. However, the analysis highlights important geographical, thematic, and taxonomic gaps that constrain the region’s capacity to achieve coherent and inclusive marine conservation outcomes.

Geographically, Cape Verde remains underrepresented in the current portfolio of initiatives, underscoring the need to promote its integration into transnational and EU–African funding mechanisms. Thematically, oceanic waters, deep-sea and benthic ecosystems, sustainable fishing and the identification of ecological corridors, KBA and VME continue to receive limited attention despite their ecological relevance, while socioeconomic and governance dimensions are less represented relative to ecological studies. Taxonomically, research remains concentrated on seabirds and some specific groups of marine megafauna in the northern archipelagos, leaving other key groups such as benthic invertebrates, elasmobranchs, non-commercial fish species and cetaceans in Cape Verde comparatively overlooked.

Beyond these thematic gaps, the fragmentation of data and monitoring systems constrains regional connectivity and long-term assessments. Strengthening interoperable sensor networks, standardized data platforms, and cross-archipelago information sharing would significantly enhance the region’s analytical capacity. Likewise, expanding transnational collaboration between African and European partners will be crucial to reduce asymmetries in capacity, resources, and access to funding.

While scientific and monitoring projects are essential for building the regional evidence base, initiatives that remain primarily at the stage of baseline studies, ecological assessment, or data production without a clear pathway toward MPA designation, management plans, enforcement, policy uptake, or participatory governance may create a bottleneck between knowledge generation and practical conservation action. A key funding opportunity therefore lies in supporting projects that translate science into implementation.

Overall, the findings reaffirm that conservation efforts in Macaronesia form part of a broader regional movement aligned with international biodiversity targets, including the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and its 30×30 objective to conserve 30% of the marine environment by 2030. Advancing these collaborations and addressing the identified gaps will be essential to position Macaronesia as a model region for integrated marine conservation and sustainable ocean governance within the Atlantic.

Macaronesia therefore represents not only a biodiversity hotspot but also a strategic governance laboratory for testing integrated approaches to marine conservation, climate resilience, and sustainable ocean management across interconnected island systems [4,7,8,14,18,19,20]. Future conservation success in the region will depend not only on increasing the number of protected areas or scientific initiatives, but also on strengthening long-term institutional cooperation, reducing regional asymmetries, integrating local

communities into governance processes, and translating scientific knowledge into durable conservation outcomes.

References

1. Arneith, A., Leadley, P., Claudet, J., Coll, M., Rondinini, C., Rounsevell, M. D., ... & Fuchs, R. (2023). Making protected areas effective for biodiversity, climate and food. *Global Change Biology*, 29(14), 3883-3894.
2. Balmford, A., Koh, L. P., Tilman, D., Possingham, H., Obura, D., & McElwee, P. (2024). Reflections on the Global Biodiversity Framework: Achievements, gaps, and future priorities. *One Earth*, 7(12), 2092-2094.
3. Castro, N., Gestoso, I., Ramalhosa, P., Lopes, E., Almeida, C., Costa, A., ... & Canning-Clode, J. (2023). Testing differences of marine non-indigenous species diversity across Macaronesia using a standardised approach. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 192, 115021.
4. Devlin, M. J., Lyons, B. P., Johnson, J. E., & Hills, J. M. (2021). The tropical Pacific Oceanscape: Current issues, solutions and future possibilities. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 166, 112181.
5. Douvere, F. (2008). The importance of marine spatial planning in advancing ecosystem-based sea use management. *Marine policy*, 32(5), 762-771.
6. Fitzsimons, J. A., Garrison, K., Finnegan, B., & Luby, I. (2025). The 30× 30 protection target: Attitudes of residents from seven countries. *Sustainability*, 17(8), 3444.
7. Florencio, M., Patiño, J., Nogué, S., Traveset, A., Borges, P. A., Schaefer, H., ... & Santos, A. M. (2021). Macaronesia as a fruitful arena for ecology, evolution, and conservation biology. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 9, 718169.
8. Freitas, R., Romeiras, M., Silva, L., Cordeiro, R., Madeira, P., González, J. A., ... & Ávila, S. P. (2019). Restructuring of the ‘Macaronesia’ biogeographic unit: A marine multi-taxon biogeographical approach. *Scientific reports*, 9(1), 15792.
9. Gacutan, J., Galparsoro, I., Pınarbaşı, K., Murillas, A., Adewumi, I. J., Praphotjanaporn, T., ... & Milligan, B. M. (2022). Marine spatial planning and ocean accounting: Synergistic tools enhancing integration in ocean governance. *Marine Policy*, 136, 104936.
10. Gurney, G. G., Adams, V. M., Álvarez-Romero, J. G., & Claudet, J. (2023). Area-based conservation: Taking stock and looking ahead. *One Earth*, 6(2), 98-104.
11. Hassoun, A. E. R., Mojtahid, M., Merheb, M., Lionello, P., Gattuso, J. P., & Cramer, W. (2025). Climate change risks on key open marine and coastal mediterranean ecosystems. *Scientific Reports*, 15(1), 24907.
12. Johnson, J. E., Allain, V., Basel, B., Bell, J. D., Chin, A., Dutra, L. X., ... & Nicol, S. (2020). Impacts of climate change on marine resources in the Pacific Island region. In *Climate change and impacts in the Pacific* (pp. 359-402). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

13. Nuno, A., Madruga, L., Cameron, A., Airaud, F., Andrade, C., Nazaré, L., ... & Mulligan, B. (2024). Establishing a Marine Protected Area network using a Marine Spatial Planning approach: A reflection on practical challenges and opportunities for social–ecological integration. *Conservation Science and Practice*, 6(10), e13196.
14. Sala, E., Mayorga, J., Bradley, D., Cabral, R. B., Atwood, T. B., Auber, A., ... & Lubchenco, J. (2021). Protecting the global ocean for biodiversity, food and climate. *Nature*, 592(7854), 397-402.
15. Frazão Santos, C., Wedding, L. M., Agardy, T., Reimer, J. M., Gissi, E., & Calado, H. (2025). Marine spatial planning and marine protected area planning are not the same and both are key for sustainability in a changing ocean. *npj Ocean Sustainability*, 4(1), 23.
16. Gueroun, S. K., Javidpour, J., Andrade, C., Nogueira, N., Freitas, M., & Canning-Clode, J. (2021). Pelagic Cnidaria and Ctenophora diversity patterns and trends in Macaronesia insular systems (NE Atlantic). *Marine Biodiversity*, 51(2), 32.
17. Varela, J., Santos, C. P., Nunes, E., Pissarra, V., Pires, S., Ribeiro, B. P., ... & Rosa, R. (2025). Sharks in Cabo Verde, Canarias, Madeira and Azores islands: species richness, conservation status and anthropogenic pressures. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 12, 1490317.
18. Vince, J. (2014). Oceans governance and marine spatial planning in Australia. *Australian Journal of Maritime & Ocean Affairs*, 6(1), 5-17.
19. Zhao, C., Ge, Y., & Zheng, M. (2024). Reflections on How to Reach the “30 by 30” Target: Identification of and Suggestions on Global Priority Marine Areas for Protection. *Water*, 16(16), 2293.
20. Zittis, G., Zoumides, C., Zemah-Shamir, S., Tase, M., Zotos, S., Demirel, N., ... & Moustakas, A. (2025). Insular ecosystem services in peril: a systematic review on the impacts of climate change and other drivers. *Climatic Change*, 178(7), 127.